

Polarography of Cadmium (II) in Acetamide

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Polarograms of cadmium (II) in aqueous acetamide in presence of potassium chloride, sulphate and citrate have been studied at ionic strength ($\mu=0.2$). The observed change in $ia\eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$ suggests solvation of the cation. Preliminary inference towards this suggestion has been drawn from the electrocapillary curves.

Polarographic measurements have recently been made both in aqueous and non-aqueous media using a number of electro-reducible ions. Because of the insolubility of a great many organic compounds in water, these studies were restricted in the case of organic compounds to those which were completely or adequately miscible with water. A good deal of work, however, has been communicated¹ which refers to non-aqueous media such as acetonitriles, amides etc. Polarography of cadmium (II) itself has been studied in formamide and a few substituted amides by Hale and Parson².

In the present communication the authors have reported the results of polarographic measurements with cadmium ion in aqueous solutions of acetamide of different compositions, (0-30%) with particular reference to diffusion current as influenced by changes in viscosity and solvation. These studies have been carried out at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.2$) in the presence of potassium chloride, sulphate and citrate as supporting electrolytes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium chloride, sulphate and citrate used were of Analar grade. Acetamide, a Riedel product, was used without further purification. Double-distilled water was used for preparing the solutions. Mercury was distilled under vacuum.

Pyrex glassware was used in all the measurements. The dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) is made from a 10 cm standard imported capillary. The drop-time, t , in the open circuit and the constant pressure of mercury are given below. Temperature control at $25^{\circ}\pm 0.1^{\circ}$ was accomplished by means of a relay and a

- (a) G. H. Brown and H. Hsiung, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1960, 107, 57-58.
(b) R. C. Larson and Reynold, T. Twanioto, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 3239.
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toluene regulator. A manual polarograph (Worsley-Lancs) in conjunction with a Pye galvanometer was used for recording the potential and current respectively. Deoxygenation of the samples was done elaborately by a continuous flow of purified⁹ hydrogen from a Kipp's apparatus. Polarographic half-cell was connected through an agar-bridge to a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.)

The half-wave potential and slope were determined from the equation.

$$E_{d.m.e} = E_{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{0.0591}{n} \log \frac{i}{i_a - i} \text{ at } 25^\circ$$

Height of mercury column to the tip of capillary	= 39.60 cm
Mass (m) of mercury flowing/sec	= 3.252 mg
Drop time 't'	= 2.60 sec
Concentration of CdCl ₂	= 5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴ M
Sensitivity of the galvanometer	= 6.89 × 10 ⁻⁸ amp/div

TABLE I

Supporting electrolyte—Potassium chloride

Percentage of acetamide	<i>i</i> _a (μamp)	Slope (volts)	<i>E</i> _½ vs S. C. E. (volts)	<i>η</i> (centipoise)	<i>i</i> <i>aη</i> ^½
0	5.930	0.027	-0.606	0.900	5.622
5	5.654	„	-0.603	0.998	5.646
10	5.241	„	-0.606	1.088	5.468
15	5.102	„	-0.605	1.152	5.478
20	4.757	„	-0.611	1.366	5.559
25	4.620	„	-0.608	1.445	5.554
30	4.276	„	-0.612	1.674	5.533

TABLE II

Supporting electrolyte—Potassium sulphate

Percentage of acetamide	<i>i</i> _a (μamp)	Slope (volts)	<i>E</i> _½ vs. S. C. E. (volts)	<i>η</i> (centipoise)	<i>i</i> <i>aη</i> ^½
0	5.241	0.0245	-0.585	0.920	4.801
5	5.034	„	-0.587	1.047	6.316
10	4.827	„	-0.588	1.138	5.147
15	4.723	„	-0.588	1.245	5.879
20	4.620	„	-0.585	1.347	5.362
25	4.138	„	-0.587	1.503	5.072
30	3.656	„	-0.612	1.701	4.773

TABLE III

Supporting electrolyte—Potassium citrate

Percentage of acetamide	i_d (μ amp)	Slope (volts)	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs. S. C. E. (volts)	η (centipoise)	$i_d \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$
0	9.035	0.027	-0.647	0.935	8.734
5	8.414	"	-0.648	1.023	8.507
10	7.930	"	-0.653	1.140	8.476
15	7.447	"	-0.660	1.265	8.375
20	6.965	"	-0.661	1.391	8.215
25	6.621	"	-0.664	1.526	8.181
30	6,138	"	-0.668	1.720	8,052

DISCUSSION

Table I shows that the value of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ with potassium chloride as supporting electrolyte ranges from -0.602 to -0.611 volts and may be taken to be more or less constant. The value of the slope is 0.027 volts thereby indicating a reversible reaction. With the gradual increase in the percentage of acetamide, the diffusion coefficient of the ion is reduced and hence the diffusion current shows a regular decrease. Viscosity, however, increases with the increasing content of acetamide. But $i_d \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is not constant so that the change in diffusion coefficient 'D' which ultimately affects i_d is not solely due to viscosity changes. The varying values of $i_d \eta^{\frac{1}{2}}$ suggest that the size of the ion must have suffered a change by solvation⁴.

A similar state of affairs is envisaged in the case of potassium sulphate as supporting electrolyte (Table II). But with potassium citrate as supporting electrolyte (Table III) there is a regular shift towards the negative side in the values of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$. This may be explained by the fact that the supporting electrolyte is no longer inert but reacts with Cd (II) forming a complex.

A comparison of the results with the three supporting electrolytes suggests that the diffusion current, i_d , decreases in the order :

$$i_d(\text{K-citrate}) > i_d(\text{KCl}) > i_d(\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)$$

A study of the electrocapillary curves in presence of these supporting electrolytes has also been made. The legends given in Fig. 1 refer to the experimental conditions. It follows from these curves that the maxima in presence of 30% acetamide are considerably suppressed, whereas in absence of acetamide they

are pronounced, and the curves are almost parabolic. Surface-active non-electrolytes cause truncation⁵ of the electrocapillary curves and in many instances

the maxima are suppressed. Acetamide seems to act as a surface-active substance. This property may be attributed to its tendency to develop a dipole, as depicted below, owing to electromeric displacement⁶ within the molecule.

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